

Modeling the Consumption Response to the CARES Act

Christopher D. Carroll Edmund Crawley Jiri Slacalek
Matthew N. White

May 6, 2020

Viewpoints and conclusions stated in this paper are the responsibility of the authors alone and do not necessarily reflect the viewpoints of the Federal Reserve Board or the ECB.

econ-ark.github.io/Pandemic	<i>HTML version of paper</i>
Interactive-Jupyter-Notebook	<i>Allows user to modify some assumptions</i>
github.com/econ-ark/Pandemic	<i>Full codebase; explore all assumptions</i>
LaTeX subdirectory of ↑	<i>PDF version of paper</i>
LaTeX subdirectory of ↑	<i>Presentation slides</i>

The CARES Act directly impacts household balance sheets:

- \$1,200 to every adult (means tested)
- \$600 per week *additional* unemployment benefits, for up to 13 weeks (\$7,800)

Compared to 10 years ago, we now have good models of how household consumption responds

Contribution of paper:

- How is this time different?
- What does a carefully calibrated consumption model say?

Rich stochastic lifecycle model made up of high school dropouts, high school graduates and college graduates, matching:

- Their income profiles (trends and uncertainty)
- Liquid wealth distribution
 - matched using patience heterogeneity

⇒ Annual Marginal Propensity to Consume (MPC) ≈ 0.5

Matches *both* micro and macro phenomena

- Parker, Souleles, Johnson, and McClelland (2013)
- Fagereng, Holm, and Natvik (2017)

What's New: (1) 'Deep' Unemployment

Want to experiment with different expectations (and realities) about the length of pandemic-related unemployment.

Two types of unemployed:

- 1 'Normal' Unemployed: $2/3$ probability of finding a job each quarter - expected unemployment duration 1.5 quarters
- 2 'Deep' Unemployed: $1/3$ probability of returning to 'normal' unemployed state each quarter - expected unemployment duration 4.5 quarters

C during lockdown is restricted:

- Many types of C less desirable, or illegal
- Calibration: 11 percent C reduction (travel, restaurants, etc)
- Captured by reduction in the marginal utility of C

⇒ Households defer some of their spending into the future

Two scenarios:

- Short-Lived: 'Lockdown' lasts two quarters on average
 - unemployment 15%
 - One-third is 'deep unemployment'
- Long, Deep: The 'lockdown' lasts four quarters on average
 - unemployment 22%
 - Mostly deep unemployment

We invite you to make your own assumptions:

[Interactive-Jupyter-Notebook](#) *Allows user to modify some assumptions*
github.com/econ-ark/Pandemic *Full codebase*

Unemployment skews young, unskilled and low income

Aggregate Labor and Transfer Income

Assumes: Stimulus check delayed one qtr; 25 percent spend before check

Aggregate Consumption Response

Consumption Response Decomposition

Consumption Response By Employment Type

Consumption Response By Employment Type

Consumption Response By Employment Type

Is Targeting Useful In The Aggregate?

- Deep unemployed have lower MPCs
- UE benefits are generous - average MPC lower than marginal

Deep, Long Pandemic: Income

Deep, Long Pandemic: Consumption

Short-lived lockdown: CARES Act sufficient for swift C recovery

Long, deep lockdown: Further action to prevent big C drop

Check out the dashboard:

<https://econ-ark.org/pandemicdashboard>